

Thematic workshop proposal

1. Workshop Title
Robotic medical devices for human rehabilitation
2. Organizers
Silvia Logozzo, Department of Engineering, University of Perugia, silvia.logozzo@unipg.it
3. Workshop Format
The workshop format will primarily be based on invited speaker contributions; however, it will also be open to the submission of thematic extended abstracts, allowing for broader participation and the inclusion of additional relevant perspectives. The workshop will feature a structured format centered on keynote presentations by leading experts in the design and application of robotic medical rehabilitation devices. The 90-minute session will be entirely dedicated to invited speakers, organized into three thematic segments of 30 minutes each. Each segment will address a distinct topic related to the design criteria of robotic rehabilitation technologies, offering a comprehensive and multidisciplinary perspective on current innovations and challenges in the field.
4. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics
The workshop focuses on the design principles and rationale behind robotic devices developed for human rehabilitation and tailored to address various impairments. The development of such devices requires a multidisciplinary approach, engaging engineers, medical professionals, and physiotherapists. An innovative PICO-driven framework for the design and selection of robotic rehabilitation medical devices will be presented, alongside a comprehensive roadmap outlining the evolution and application of soft, rigid, and hybrid robotic exoskeletons for hand rehabilitation.
5. Keywords
Rehabilitation robotics
Robotic medical devices
PICO model
Robot-assisted therapy
Robot design
6. Preferred Date
17 October
7. List of Speakers (*Include names, affiliations, and indicate if each speaker is confirmed or to be confirmed.*)
 - **Maria Cristina Valigi** – Confirmed
Department of Engineering, University of Perugia
 - **Cinzia Amici** – Confirmed
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Meccanica e Industriale, University of Brescia
 - **Monica Malvezzi** – Confirmed (either herself or another speaker from her institution)
Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione e Scienze Matematiche, University of Siena

- **Nicola Secciani** – Confirmed (either himself or another speaker from his institution)
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Industriale, University of Firenze
- **Monica Tiboni** – Confirmed
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Meccanica e Industriale, University of Brescia

8. Expected Number of Attendees
30

9. Target Audience
General public, therapists for rehabilitation, medical doctors, engineers, patients, manufacturers, psychologists. The workshop will serve as a platform to foster connections between the academic community and the industrial sector, promoting collaboration and knowledge transfer across research and application domains.

10. Workshop Outcomes (*E.g., publications, videos, special issues, future events.*)
A key expected outcome of the workshop is the establishment of collaborative partnerships among professionals and researchers in the field of robotic human rehabilitation. The exchange of knowledge and expertise fostered during the event will serve as a catalyst for future advancements in the discipline and will lay the groundwork for the organization of subsequent initiatives.

11. Plan for Special Issue or Session (*Describe your plan to organize a special issue or session after the conference. Priority will be given to workshop proposals that include a clear plan to organize a special issue in the months after the conference in a venue relevant to the I-RIM community and focused on the workshop topic.*)

Following this workshop, we aim to initiate the publication of new research contributions in the field, organize dedicated special tracks at upcoming conferences, and promote special issues in leading international journals of relevance to the I-RIM community.

12. Call for Extended Abstracts

A specific call for thematic extended abstracts is envisaged. All the topics will be displayed on the workshop webpage and authors will be invited using specific mailing lists or by personal knowledge. The main topics of the call will be:

- Design challenges and outcomes of robotic rehabilitation devices
- Emerging technologies for robotic human rehabilitation
- Robotic medical devices for rehabilitation of different body districts
- Clinical trials for device accreditation in compliance with traditional medical device regulations.
- Clinical and at-home robot-assisted rehabilitation: new directions and issues

13. Workshop Webpage (*Provide the link or planned location. This will be linked in the I-RIM program.*)
The webpage link will be provided after the eventual acceptance of this proposal

14. Notes on Registration (*Indicate how you plan to use the 2 free one-day registrations and manage additional speaker registrations.*)

I plan to offer the 2 free one-day registrations to 2 of the speakers. The other speakers will purchase at least a one-day pass.